

Sexual offending in university staff settings - a systematic review

McCashin, Darragh – School of Psychology, Dublin City University

Indicate your track:

(Underline the track, which suits your abstract the most. You can select more than one track)

1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 - a. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
 - b. Institutional interventions and policies**
 - c. Policy-Level insights**
2. Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Length: 310 words

Background

Increasingly, different workplaces, cultural spaces and social media are witnessing various forms of controversy and multilevel responses pertaining to the prevalence of sexual harassment and sexual offending across jurisdictions (Ranganathan, Wamoyi, Pearson, & Stöckl, 2021). The focus of this review is on the university environment. A full literature review will be presented to contextualise the unique setting that is the university ecosystem when tackling sexual offending.

Method

This paper is a systematic review which descriptively analysed the peer-reviewed research literature on an understudied population within university-based sexual offending, that of university staff. A total of 9 studies were included in the final analysis from a total of six countries, with a combined sample of 2,319 academic staff. Both quantitative and qualitative studies were included.

Results

Studies took the form of a quantitative survey (n=6); but other studies also utilised secondary data analysis to interrogate perpetration and victimisation rates (n=2), or qualitative interviews (n=1). Where data was available and suitable, a combined mean prevalence rate of

22.81% was calculated. These findings broadly mirror the high and concerning prevalence rates of sexual offences across different student populations in various localities (Anderson et al., 2021; Hales & Gannon, 2021; McMahon, Wood, Cusano, & Macri, 2019). One distinct difference between the literature on academic staff and student populations is the sheer weight of evidence for the latter group. Study quality was highly variable and mean conclusive insights are limited, as well as problematic variability in operationalised definitions of sexual offending. Meta-analytic approaches to the data are presently ongoing.

Conclusion and implications

Notwithstanding several significant methodological caveats, the findings are discussed in the context of practical prevention and intervention strategies that are ongoing in some regions, in addition to future options to promote a safer university system for all. This will chime with much of the work across each of ReMO's three working groups.